

Short Commentary on Composite Materials in Japan

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It is my pleasure to have a chance to offer a short presentation on the problem areas for challenge of composite materials. But within a short time allowed, it would be confined to only a briefing of FRP status and a few topics.

1. FRP industry in Japan in 1974

The total amount of Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics (GFRP) products was around 210,000 tons in 1973 and it was expected to reach 400,000 tons or more in 1974. But due to the oil crisis of 1974, ca 40% of the estimated amount was scarcely accomplished.

The share of the total amount of 150,000 tons is: (1) FRP-corrugated roof plates: 1×10^4 tons, (2) bath tub: 2.7×10^4 tons, (3) septic tanks and sanitary tanks: 3×10^4 tons, (4) boat: 2.2×10^4 tons, (5) tanks and cooling towers: ca 1×10^4 tons, (6) industrial goods: 1.7×10^4 tons, (7) sporting goods: ca 1×10^4 tons, (8) miscellaneous including BMC, SMC-car parts: 2.7×10^4 tons.

As to the other composite materials except GFRP, several new exploitations have been tried as followed: speaker cone, artificial limb, black shaft, alpolite plate (aluminum + polymer + aluminum sandwich plate), thin iron film (20 μ thick), high acoustic damping panel (made of gypsum and foil), CF+GF hybrid cloth, ski, boat, GFRP-joint of concrete piles, BMC and SMC mouldings and so on.

2. Since in Japan the natural resources are very limited, the development of highly advanced materials and reproducible composites are urgently needed.

3. In Japan, the attack of big earthquakes is being warned. For the development of earthquake-proof houses and buildings, it is needed to design such structures so as to be of light weight, high stiffness and damping. For such purposes, the use of composite materials and the introduction of composition concepts in those designs are extremely useful.

4. As the final aspect, I would like to inform you that we are now establishing a new "Japan Society of Composite Materials" which we will start on June 6th, 1975. This will be a large challenge by composites to science and technology in future.